

////////////////////////////////////

CULTURAL DIFFERENCES & NEW PRODUCT OPPORTUNITIES: THAI INDOOR MOBILITY AIDS

Praima Israsena, Nuanny Boonvong
Department of Industrial Design, Faculty of Architecture
Chulalongkorn University, Thailand
praima.is@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ability to move reduces with ageing. Indoor mobility has become the main factor for assessing safety and quality of life. Suitable mobility aids decrease the risk of falling and the intensity of elder care burden. Thai culture and economy are important barriers to the Western mobility aids adoption, leading to eldercare failure. This research aims to study barriers to adopting Western mobility aids in Thailand, and to identify opportunities for new product development. Techniques for this research include contextual interview, self-documentary study, and Q-sorting. Findings on cultural differences suggest new product requirements appropriate to the Thai context. The results of this research could impact the quality of life of the elderly and their families in both Thailand and other developing countries in the region. The integrated opportunity identification approaches explored in this research could be beneficial to any cultural-specific new product development.

Keywords: indoor mobility, elder care, new product development, opportunity identification, cultural difference

INTRODUCTION

Ageing involves degenerative processes in musculoskeletal, neuromuscular and sensory systems, which reduce performance, perception and the ability to cope with the environment (Horac et al., 1989) and augment difficulties in daily life of the elderly (Guralnic et al., 1989). Ability to move reduces with ageing, and one third of the home-living elderly fall at least once per year (Luukinen et al., 1994). Falls are the leading cause of nonfatal

injuries and injurious death among older adults; the aftermath of a fall stresses the health care system and places financial and psychological burdens on the elderly and family. Because of this, fall prevention is a primary focus of numerous health care agendas (Fabre et al., 2010). Indoor mobility has become the main factor for assessing safety. Problems with mobility are prevalent in the older population (Regnier et al., 1980; Zimmer & Chappell, 1994). Developing suitable mobility aids equipment that helps in elder care is one strategy that can decrease the intensity of elder care burden in 3 ways: extending the seniors' functional independency in the household, preventing accidents that would lead to physical dependency, and minimizing the caregivers' stress and burden as well as failure, which can lead to abandonment. Throughout the years, Thailand has adopted elder-care products from foreign countries, particularly developed Western countries. However, only some parts of those products can be applied to the Thai context. As in most Asian countries, Thai family is the traditional social institution for elder care (Siriboon, 1998). Commonly Thai elder care is practiced by untrained family caregivers. Thai ways of life and economy are important barriers to the application of western design. For example, sleeping on the floor makes it difficult for the elderly to get up and use a wheelchair. Not only is adopting foreign products not suitable, but also creates an even greater burden with financial and mental stress. These cultural barriers are left unexplored and sometimes lead to the failure in elder care (Sithitri, 1985). Mobility assistive products have substantial socioeconomic costs for the society (Fifield & Fifield, 1997), impacting the elderly and their families' quality of life. Suitable mobility aids equipment that

has not been explored in the West, is thus needed. The cultural barriers to adopting Western product open opportunities for new product development.

CULTURAL DIFFERENCE & PRODUCT OPPORTUNITY

Product innovation can be defined broadly as a new match between a need and a solution. The novelty can be in the solution or the need - or in a new match of an existing need and an existing solution (Terwiesch & Ulrich, 2009)

“Opportunity” is the chance to meet a market need (or want) through a creative combination of resources to deliver superior value (Kirzner, 1973; Casson, 1982). Opportunity may be an “imprecisely-defined market need, or un- or under-employed resources or capabilities” (Kirzner, 1997). It may include basic technologies, inventions for which no market has been defined, or ideas for products or services. Even if prospective customers may not be able to articulate their needs, interests, or problems, they may still be able to recognize the value of new product when they are presented with it and have its benefits explained (Von Hippel, 1994). Opportunity identification is among the most important areas of very successful innovation (Brem and Voigt, 2009). The processes of opportunity identification that appear in most literature can be categorized in to 3 groups: 1). Sensing or perceiving market or prospective customers’ needs, 2). Recognizing under-employed resources or technology, and 3) Discovering or creating a new “fit” between particular market needs and specified resources.

Sensing and understanding market needs has been identified as a critical success factor and a top priority for new product development (Cooper et al, 2004; Kleef et al, 2005). These involve research methods such as lead users, extreme users which are related to user-centered design. The benefit of involving lead users in the product development process was pointed out by Von Hippel (1988). Lead users are a group of users who face new needs ahead of the market and highly benefit from the use of product and acquire certain knowledge so much as to alter products themselves in order to answer their unmet future needs. Capability and motivation of lead users’ creation provide useful data that led to insights for emerging products, and their needs can

be leading indicators of future products (Urban and von Hippel, 1988; Luthje and Herstatt, 2004). On the other hands, extreme users are those identified as the outliers of the product users’ bell shape curve. While the average customers are at the middle, extreme users are at the left and right extreme of the axis (IDEO, 2011). Others argued and defined extreme users differently, for example, Rothwell and Gardiner (1983) stated that innovation may derive from extreme need of extreme users within extreme environment. Unlike lead users who create solutions themselves, extreme users only provide inspiration for professional designers, who develop the solutions.

Recognizing un-employed resources, especially for the Thai cultural-specific product development, maybe related to designing with appropriated technology. Appropriate technology is generally recognized as encompassing technological choice and application that is small scale, labor intensive, energy efficient, environmentally sound and locally controlled (Hazeltine & Bull, 1999) Both Schumacher and many modern-day proponents of appropriate technology also emphasize the technology as people centered (Akubue, 2002).

Discovering the new “fit” for the Thai cultural-specific product development might be closely related to design areas such as design for the bottom of the pyramid or BoP. “The bottom of the pyramid” (Prahalad, 2002; Hart, 2005) points out the existence of a huge untapped customer base in the world’s poor areas. The bottom of the pyramid is the largest, but poorest socio-economic group, the 2.5 billion people who live on less than \$2.50 per day. The terms “bottom of the pyramid”, “base of the Pyramid”, or “BoP” are used in particular for projects that deliberately target that demographic, and often use new technology. The BoP design principles include: learning everything possible about a specific engineering, economic, cultural, and social context; creating “transparent” technologies that end users can easily understand, use, and innovate upon; limiting costs and environmental impact by reducing material use; providing skills and not just finished technologies to empower users; and aiming for scale to achieve impact in terms of numbers. As poor people are not averse to buying products that can change their lives dramatically, the low-cost, high-

value, well-distributed and indigenously produced products for the poor could account the highest volume share in the market (Prahalad, 2002; Hart, 2005).

While these design techniques and areas have contributed greatly to opportunity identification, each of them primarily concentrates on only one of the various aspects. This research explored these techniques during data gathering and opportunity analyzing phases. Drawing from the cross-disciplinary theoretical base, this paper also discusses integrated product identification approaches suitable for the cultural-specific product development.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of this research are:

- 1) to study barriers to adopting Western mobility aids products to daily elder care activities in Thailand.
- 2) to identify opportunities for new mobility aids product development that are suitable for Thailand and other developing countries in the region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Techniques for this research include self-documentary study, contextual interview and observation, and Q-sorting. The subjects include 50 pairs of elderlies and caregivers who were carefully chosen on the basis of age, gender, length of dependency, the relationship to each other, the elderly person's functional dependency in ADL, living conditions, and equipment used for elder care.

SELF-DOCUMENTARY STUDY

In order to collect information of real daily activities, subjects were asked to record details of mobility challenges in a diary with questions for the causes of the elderly's dependency, the schedule of daily activities of the elderly and the caregiver in 24 hours, and details on mobility. The caregiver was to record the steps in mobility-related activity, problems in each step, the advantages and disadvantages of the products used, using a digital camera to record pictures, and provide a description attached to the pictures. This method of data collection using a diary has many advantages, namely: 1) Giving the subjects time to describe the problems as they arise while they are fresh in their

memory and to be highly accurate, 2) Getting information and pictures of activities that are highly personal, where the elderlies and the caregivers are more comfortable in describing in the diary more than having a researcher carry out an observation in their homes, 3) Enabling data collection from subjects living in remote provinces by mailing in the diaries without time and travel costs. However, the difficulty in this method of data collection is that many caregivers have insufficient language skills to read the questions and write the answers in the diary. Many caregivers also prefer to give information in a face-to-face interview.

CONTEXTUAL INTERVIEW & OBSERVATION

To get information in the real context, researchers went in to observe and interview elderlies and caregivers during daily care activities. The interview consisted of questions similar to the self-documentary study. The advantages of this method are 1) Allowing the researcher to ask questions as real events happen, giving an in-depth understanding, 2) Getting information, photographs, and video of high quality by professional researchers, 3) Overcoming language barriers by letting the subjects talk, which is more effective as they are better at speaking than reading and writing. (in case caregivers prefer to give information in a face-to-face interview)

The information from the self-documentary study and contextual interview and observation is processed using qualitative analysis methods in the form of tables and diagrams. The pairs of elderlies and caregivers were grouped using the Barthel ADL Index as a reference to analyze the relationships between the challenges in mobility and the living conditions as well as the equipment used.

Q-SORTING

The Q-sorting technique was employed to study the factors in deciding to buy or use mobility related equipment, including value perception of products and environment related to care giving. The research team selected variety images of mobility aids that are in the market. Picture cards were organized according to each step in mobility: sitting/sleeping, getting up to sit/stand, moving horizontally, and going upstairs. The subjects were

to select the set that was relevant to them, for example, those who are not using the stairs would skip the stair-ascending set. Each set consists of 15 product images with brief descriptions, carefully chosen to provide variety and receive the value of -2, -1, 0, 1, 2 along a bi-polar scale of 8 qualities: “help the caregivers to assist the elderly more easily/allow the elderly to function independently”, “looks homey/clinical”, “looks pretty/functional”, “looks Thai/foreign”, “looks familiar/unfamiliarly innovative”, “compatible/standing out”, “temporary/permanent”, “looks inexpensive/expensive”, and “compact/large”. During the collection of data, subjects were asked to sort the picture cards into 3 piles with 5 images per pile under favorable, unfavorable, and indifferent. They were then asked to select 2 images that are most favorable from 5 images in the favorable pile, and 2 images that are most unfavorable from 5 images in the unfavorable pile. They were also asked to give reasons for the selections of equipment.

The preference scores were analyzed and correlated with the bi-polar scale of 8 qualities in order to explain the factors determining the decisions to modify the living space and use certain mobility aids.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The study found that most families with purchasing power in the city, where the Western lifestyle were adopted, are using imported solutions and are facing many problems in elder care similar to those of the West. On the other hand, low-income families who both live in the city and the countryside have to deal with problems that are specific to Thailand which are left unexplored and unsolved. With the limited space, this paper is not describing the big picture or illustrating all the problems found in Thailand, but will focus only on the problems that are specific to the country that have severe effects on the elderly’s caregivers.

PROBLEMS & UNMET NEEDS

The activities in taking care of the elderly’s mobility can be mainly divided into changing from the sleeping position to sitting, standing, moving, and going up the stairs. Each activity may involve walking by themselves, using a walker/other mobility

aids equipments, or relying on either the caregiver or the environment, such as seated sliding on the floor.

1. The activities in helping with the elderly’s mobility differ from those generally found in the West in that Thai houses are quite small and narrow, so the use of walkers and wheelchairs is not always possible. Although caregivers try to clear pathways by moving things around, some areas such as small bathrooms still provide no access.
2. The narrowness of Thai houses also result in beds being placed along the wall This makes it hard for caregivers to help the elderly up, and forces them to exert energy in uncomfortable postures. Some caregivers are not able to lift the elderly, so they have to stand on the bed in order to pull up the elderly. This is against Thai traditions that forbid standing over older persons.
3. Small bathrooms without separated wet and dry areas are dangerously slippery. In many homes, there is not enough space to bring in any mobility aids (such as a walker, a wheelchair, or a shower chair). Without the installation of grab bars, elderly have to stand holding on to the wall-hung sink that is not stable. In cases where the elderly cannot stand up, they are seated on the toilet to bathe. In both cases, it is difficult for the elderly to maintain balance and move around.
4. Thais tend to use a space for various functions, and prefer foldable and mobile furniture. The elderly usually hold on to furniture as they move around the house, but foldable tables are not steady and thus are unsafe.
5. Many low-income Thais living around the fringe of the city and in the countryside choose to sleep on the floor for fear of falling off the bed, having to pay for a bed, and losing living space. The advantage of the sleeping mat is that it can be folded away to make room for other activities. On the other hand, the elderly who sleep on the floor are not able to get up by themselves and rely on the caregivers more often. Some elderly try to help themselves by sliding seated on the floor, which is slow and difficult. Sleeping on the floor greatly affects caregivers as they must bend down to help all the time. This requires much energy and forces uncomfortable positions. In addition, it also exerts a

lot of energy in helping the elderly from the lying position to the sitting and standing position. In helping the elderly to sit down on the floor, the caregiver has to gently lower the elderly onto the floor to prevent falling. Moving the elderly from the floor to sit in a chair or a wheelchair is very difficult. Instead, the caregiver makes room for the elderly to sit against the wall, stretching out their legs, for various activities such as eating.

To move the elderly, caregivers choose to pull the elderly on the floor. Some drag them by the mat on which they are lying. Some caregivers only pull by the body, so the elderly gets scraped and bruised by the floor and the surrounding objects as they are moved across the floor.

Other less severe problems found in the study include:

6. Many families move the elderly to sleep in the living room. The consequence is that the elderly has to use the maid's bathroom or guest bathroom, which is very small and far from the sleeping area. This requires the caregivers to help the elderly in a longer distance to the bathroom, giving a burden to both the caregivers and the elderly. Staying in the living room, the elderly also need to sit up more frequently to interact with others, relying more often on others to assist.
7. For very thin elderly, a cushion is placed on the chair and the toilet seat to prevent sitting discomfort. The caregiver must use one hand to hold on to the elderly or the cushion, and the other hand to assist the elderly such as to water and soap them in a very challenging way.
8. Thai elderly are used to wearing wrap-around cloths instead of pants, and the cloths often come off while switching positions. The elderly try to grab the cloth, and thus lose balance or put their weight on the caregiver. In addition, unlike pants, the wrap-around cloths do not allow the caregivers a secure hold and control while assisting the elderly.
9. Some elderly refuse to use walkers and other equipment because they do not want to look like patients. Some like to make up their own devices such as using a broomstick as a walker, giving the caregivers safety concerns.
10. The Thai caregivers who are close relatives of the elderly are very concerned about the elderly. They want to encourage the elderly to walk by

themselves (using equipment), but the elderly cannot get up and sit down easily as they cannot estimate distances, so the caregivers have to direct and watch them at all times,

PREFERENCES IN MOBILITY AIDS SOLUTIONS

Besides the general mobility-aids design solutions for safety, ergonomics, and comfort that are universally considered important, this research also studied certain qualities showing specific preferences in Thailand. The 8 bi-polar qualities studies in this research include "help the caregivers to assist the elderly more easily/allow the elderly to function independently", "looks homey/clinical", "looks pretty/functional", "looks Thai/foreign", "looks familiar/ unfamiliarly innovative", "compatible/ standing out", "temporary/permanent", "looks inexpensive/expensive", and "compact/large".

In general, most Thais choose solutions that help the caregivers assist the elderly more easily, rather than help the elderly to function independently. However, for mobility inside the bathroom, they prefer solutions that enable the elderly to function independently with privacy. Especially for transferring and bathing that put elderly at risk of slipping down, most Thais choose solutions that are large, long lasting, safe and easy to use.

Interestingly, for other indoor areas, Thais tend to choose solutions that are large and easy to use only during usage, while can be folded and stored easily after use, such as foldable tables, chairs, wheelchairs, and shower chairs. In addition, Thais tend to choose solutions that look homey, Thai, pretty, familiar, and inexpensive.

Interestingly, the Q-sort preference results show some conflicts between elderly and caregivers, and even among caregivers: the elderly's children or grandchildren, life partners, and hired caregivers. Most of the elderly prefer solutions that are visually prominent, large, and easy to use. The life partners prefer solutions that look Thai, familiar, and homey, where the younger family members choose devices that look innovative and clinical, similar to those from Western countries. Hired caregivers prefer solutions that allow the elderly to function independently, whereas family caregivers and the elderly tend to choose those that help the caregivers assist the elderly more easily. However,

hired caregivers usually have no authority in purchasing elder-care equipments. Even if they have a different preference, they must comply with the products chosen by the families.

The data from in-depth interviews with subjects during Q-sorting suggested that the preferences that are of conflict may be originated from generation gap, the level of affection to the elderly, the experience with innovative solutions and Western lifestyle. These often overlooked understanding of preferences that are of conflict can be used to develop new design requirements to meet the needs and to promote caregivers and elderly's well-being.

USER INNOVATION IN THE THAI CONTEXT

During the data gathering phase, the findings showed that domestic mobility aids products are actually developed or at least refined by elderly and/or caregivers. When the Thai elderly and caregivers face problems that the majority of consumers do not, globally, they have no choice but to develop their own modifications to existing products, or entirely new products, to solve their issues. User innovations found in this research can be grouped into 2 degrees: innovation of use and innovation in configuration of existing products and technologies. Innovations of use found in this research are such as: a) tying a cloth onto a clothing rail to assist self pulling up, while changing position from lying on the floor to standing, and b). dragging the elderly by the mat to move horizontally without getting up from the floor, and c) using a belt to provide a secure hold

mat to enable horizontal moving without getting up from the floor. User innovations in configuration of existing products and technologies found in this study are such as: c) using a belt to provide a secure hold and control during transfer, and d) modifying a broomstick or a cleaning mob into a cane or a walker. Systematically analysis of user innovation, especially the innovation of use, leads to the new product requirements. It greatly benefits opportunity identification for the new product development.

CULTURAL DIFFERENCE & OPPORTUNITY

Besides considering the elderly's physical and cognitive factors as usually done in general, the finding shows that the new mobility-aids product requirements specific to Thailand are mostly drawn from the origins and problems related to cultural, social, environmental and economic factors:

Cultural factors

- a. Lifestyle Practices: sleeping and dining on the floor, wearing a sarong instead of pants
- b. Customs: the forbiddance of standing and passing things over the elderly's head,
- c. Preferences and Attitudes: not favoring things to be permanently installed and things that need a technician to install (e.g. a grab bar), not favoring buying a whole product but preferring to buy parts to retrofit to existing products in the household, preferring to modify things or to find a short cut and save costs without considering the consequences.

Figure 1. User Innovation: a) tying a cloth onto a clothing rail to assist self pulling up, b) dragging the elderly by the mat to move horizontally without getting up from the floor, c) using a belt to provide a secure hold

Factors	Culture differences	Problems *						New product requirements
		a	n	p	b	t	e	
Cultural factors: a. lifestyle practices	sleeping and dining on the floor	*	*	*				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . assist in changing positions from lying to sitting and standing . enable safe, fast and easy horizontal moving while lying/sitting on the floor . allow suitable postures in transferring and moving . require less energy in transferring and moving . prevent fall or reduce impact while changing from standing to lying on the floor
	wearing a sarong instead of pants				*			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . provide a secure hold and control during transfers
b. customs	the forbiddance of standing over the elderly's head		*	*		*		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . enable body pulling up without standing on the bed/ over the elderly's head
c. attitudes and preferences (related to economic limitation)	not favoring things to be permanently installed and things that need a technician to install (e.g. a grab bar)				*		*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . easy to install . non-permanent
	preferring to modify things or to find a short cut and save costs without considering the consequences				*		*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . affordable or use appropriated technology . allow modification or customization
	not favoring buying a whole product but preferring to buy parts to retrofit to existing products in the household				*		*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . provide parts for product retrofit
Social factors	moving the mobility impaired elderly to sleep in the living room to be surrounded by family		*	*				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . allow safe, easy and fast position changing from lying to sitting and/or standing
Environmental factors (related to economic limitation)	placing a side of the bed against a wall (caregiver stands on bed to pull up the elderly)	*	*	*		*		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . enable body pulling up without standing on the bed/over the elderly's head
	use multi-functional space, prefer foldable/mobile furniture				*		*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . allow stabled grab or body holding while moving around
	small and narrow house	*						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . allow accessibility in small and narrow space
	small, narrow bathroom with no separated wet and dry areas	*	*	*	*			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . allow usage in small, wet, slippery and uneven areas
Problems*:	a=limited accessibility, n= exert energy, p= uncomfortable postures, b= risk to losing balance, t= against traditions, e = economic limitation							

Table 1. Culture differences leading to new product requirements

Social Factors

A higher importance is given to social interaction with family members than for privacy, such as moving the elderly, who cannot use stairs, to sleep in the living room downstairs in order to be surrounded with family members all the time, leading to mixed use of space and belongings.

Environmental factors

Thailand is a tropical country with very warm weather and mosquitoes. Most people cannot

afford all-day air conditioning. As most houses are quite small, Thai people in the countryside choose to sleep on the floor, while many urban inhabitants who have beds tend to place the side of the bed along the wall. This space arrangement makes it difficult to care for the elderly. Many move the elderly to sleep in the living room downstairs, forcing all to share the space. The elderly then must use the guest bathroom that is very small, does not have separate wet and dry

areas, and is far from their bed. Normally, Thais tend to use a space for various functions by moving things in and out according to activities, so they do not like to install anything large permanently, but prefer foldable and mobile furniture, such as foldable table and chairs.

Economics Factors

Financial limitations make it difficult to afford costly products. This factor causes people to find other ways to solve problems, which have both good and bad results in elder care. The economics factors greatly affect decisions on environmental arrangement and consumers' behaviors.

New product requirements drawn from these factors are as shown on Table 1

OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION APPROACHES FOR CULTURAL-SPECIFIC PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

This study has explored various opportunity identification approaches and methods, drawing from the cross-disciplinary theoretical base. Some can be directly applied to the cultural-specific product development, while some needed to be redefined and adapted. The integrated approaches employed in this study could be applied to any other design projects related to culture differences.

“Lead users” are usually defined as a group of users who face new needs ahead of the market and acquire certain knowledge, especially in terms of technologies. For the cultural-specific product development, the method could be adapted.

“Lead users” should be re-defined as “lead cultural-specific users”, who face new needs ahead of the market because of the cultural difference, and alter solutions themselves in order to answer those unmet needs.

The lead user method can be used to systematically learn about user innovation in order to apply it in new product development. While most user innovation is concentrated in use and configuration of existing products and technologies, and is a normal part of long term innovation, technologies that are easier for users to change and innovate with are making it much easier for user innovation to occur and have an impact, especially in the developing countries.

Extreme users are normally referred to the outliers of the product users' bell shape curve, in terms of physical capabilities. For the cultural-specific product development, extremeness of users should also be considered in terms of economics limitation and cultural specific.

Innovation may derive from extreme need of extreme users within extreme environment. Although extreme users only provide inspiration for professional designers and do not create solutions themselves like lead users, they provide useful data that leads directly to new product requirements.

User-centered design, appropriate technology, and the bottom of the pyramid approaches are directly beneficial to the cultural-specific product development, especially for users with economics limitation. However, these approaches tend to concentrate mainly on certain aspects. Using integrated approaches give best results for opportunity identification and product development derived from cultural differences.

CONCLUSION

Elder mobility in Thailand has specific problems rooted in cultural, social, environmental, and economic factors. The adoption of methods and devices from abroad has limitations in application, and some even lead to more complex problems. These cultural barriers to adopting Western product open opportunities for new product development. The research findings suggested new product requirements that are appropriate to the economics, cultural, and lifestyle context in Thailand. The results of this research could impact the quality of life of the elderly and their families in both Thailand and other developing countries in the region. The integrated opportunity identification approaches explored in this study can also be applied in other cultural-specific product development.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work (AS576A) was supported by the Higher Education Research Promotion and National Research University Project of Thailand, Office of the Higher Education Commission.

REFERENCES

- Akubue, A. (2000). "Appropriate Technology for Socioeconomic Development in Third World Countries". The *Journal of Technology Studies* 26 (1): 33-43.
- Brem, A. and Voigt, K.I. (2007) Innovation Management in Emerging Technology ventures: The concept of an integrated idea management. *International Journal of Technology, Policy and Management*. 7(3): 304 - 321.
- Casson, M., 1982. *The Entrepreneur*. Barnes and Noble Books, Totowa, NJ.
- Cooper, R. G., Edgett, S. J., and Kleinschmidt, E. J. (2004). Benchmarking best NPD practices III. *Research Technology Management*. 24(6): 43-55.
- Fabre, J., Ellis, R., Kosma, M., Wood, RH. (2010) Falls Risk Factors and a Compendium of Falls Risk Screening Instruments. *Journal of Geriatric Physical Therapy*; Vol 33: 184-197.
- Fifield, M.G., Fifield, M.B. (1997) Education and training individuals involved in delivery of assistive technology devices. *Technology and Disability*: 6:77-88.
- Hazeltine, B., Bull, C. (1999) *Appropriate Technology: Tools, Choices, and Implications*. New York: Academic Press.
- Guralnic, J.M., LaGroix, A.Z., Everet, D.F., Kovar M.G. (1989) Ageing in the eighties: the prevalence of comorbidity and its association with disability. *Advance data from vital and health statistics*; no 170. Hyattsville, Maryland: National Center for Health Statistics, USA.
- Hart, S.L. (2005) *Capitalism at the Crossroads*. New Jersey, Pearson Education, Inc.
- Horac, F.B., Shubert, C.H., Mirka, A. (1989) Components of Postural Dyscontrol in the Elderly: A Review *Neurobiology of Ageing*; 10:727-738.
- IDEO (2011). <http://www.ideo.com/work/myford-touch>
- Kirzner, I.M. (1973) *Competition and Entrepreneurship*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL.
- Kirzner, I.M., (1997) *Entrepreneurial discovery and the competitive market process*. *J.Econ.Lit.* 35, 60-85.
- Kleef, E. V., von Trijp, H. C. M., Luning, P. (2005). Consumer research in the early stages of new product development: a critical review of methods and techniques. *Food Quality and Preference* 16: 181-201.
- Luthje, C., and Herstatt, C. (2004). The Lead User Method: an outline of empirical findings and issues for future research. *R&D Management*. 34(5): 553-567.
- Luukinen, H., Koski, K., Hiltunen, L., Kivela, S.L. (1994) Incidence rate of falls in aged population in northern Finland. *J Clin Epidemiol* ;47:843-850.
- Prahalad, C.K. (2002) "Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid," *Strategy & Business*, no. 26.
- Regnier, V., Gordon, S., Murakami, E. (1980) *How neighborhood characteristics affect travel patterns*. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Department of Transportation:118-26.
- Siriboon, S. (1998) Problems and Needs of the Elderly's Caregivers. *Proceedings of Elderly-care Development Conference*, 25-41
- Sithitri, W. (1985) Financial and Social Problems and Needs of The Elderly and Social Changes. *Proceedings of Thai Elderly Conference*, Population Studies Institute, Chulalongkorn University and the Office of the National Economic and Social Development Board.
- Terwiesch, C., Ulrich, K.T. (2009) *Innovation Tournaments*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press
- Von Hippel, E. (1986). Lead users: A source of novel product concepts. *Management Science* 32(7): 791-805.
- Von Hippel, E. (1994) "sticky information" and the locus of problem solving: implications for innovation. *Manage.Sci.*40 (4), 429-439
- Zimmer, Z., Chappell, N.L. (1994) Mobility restriction and the use of devices among seniors. *Journal of Aging and Health* 6(2):185-208.